

ISic3687

I.Sicily inscription 3687

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Castel di Tusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Di Giovanni, V. 1885. La tavola alesina scoperta nel sec. XVI e il frammento trovato nel 1885. *ASS*. 10: 123-219. At 128

Facella, A. 2006. *Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica*. Pisa. At 289

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388958>